

O-ALDEHYDCARBOXYLIC ACIDS. PART IV. SYNTHESIS OF 5 : 6-METHYLENEDIOXYPHTHALALDEHYDIC ACID

By S. N. CHAKRAVARTI

5 : 6-Methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid for the synthesis of which numerous attempts have been made including one by Perkin and Trikojus has been synthesised :

5 : 6-Methylenedioxyhomophthalic acid, synthesised by an improved method, was oxidised in boiling xylene solution by means of selenium dioxide to 5 : 6-methylenedioxyphthalonic acid and which was converted into 5 : 6-methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid, m.p. 155°, through its sodium bisulphite compound. This acid gave on reduction 5 : 6-methylenedioxyphthalaldehyde, m.p. 227° and starting from this important acid Cryptopine and Protopine have been synthesised.

5 : 6-Methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid* for the synthesis of which an unsuccessful attempt was made by Perkin and Trikojus (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2926) and which has been obtained by Manske by the hydrolysis of bicuculline, an alkaloid occurring in *Corydalis semipervirens* and *Adlumia fungosa* (*Canad. J. Res.*, 1933, 8, 142) has now been synthesised by methods similar to those employed in the case of opianic acids and 4 : 5-methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid (Chakravarti *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 715, 873 ; 1940, 18, 264).

5 : 6-Methylenedioxy-homophthalic acid (I) was prepared by a slight modification of the method of Haworth, Perkin and Stevens (*J Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1764) and oxidised in boiling xylene solution by means of selenium dioxide to 5 : 6-methylenedioxyphthalonic acid (II), which was converted into 5 : 6-methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid (III), m.p. 155° through its sodium bisulphite compound.

The acid (III) gave on reduction 5 : 6-methylenedioxyphthalaldehyde (IV), m.p. 227°.

The further characterisation of this important acid and the synthesis of cryptopine and protopine starting from this acid is reserved for a future communication.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

5 : 6-Methylenedioxyhomophthalic Acid (I).—Carefully purified β -piperonylpropionic acid, m.p. 87-89°, was brominated in acetic acid medium and the purified bromo-acid cyclised to the corresponding bromohydrindone by the method of Haworth, Perkin and Stevens (*loc. cit.*). The isonitroso derivative of the hydrindone was prepared in the following manner, which is more convenient than the method described by Perkin and co-workers.

The hydrindone (10 g.) was dissolved in hot benzene (50 c.c.) and isoamyl nitrite (15 g) added with stirring. To the mixture concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) was added and the whole kept at 50° for an hour when the isonitroso compound gradually separated from the solution in an almost quantitative yield.

[* Nomenclature after Beilstein].

The isonitroso derivative was converted into bromopiperonyl nitrile in the following manner.

The isonitroso compound (1.4 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (14 c.c. of 10%) and treated gradually with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (2 g.). The whole mixture was heated for about 15 minutes on the water-bath when a clear solution was obtained. On cooling, the sodium salt of the nitrile, which is rather sparingly soluble in cold water, separated. The precipitated salt was filtered, collected and dissolved in a little hot water and the hot aqueous solution acidified when the nitrile was precipitated in a pure state. More of the nitrile (less pure) was obtained by acidifying the mother-liquor from the first precipitate.

The nitrile was then hydrolysed to 6-bromo-5:6-methylenedioxyhomophthalic acid by means of 10% sodium hydroxide and the bromo-acid dehalogenated by the method of Haworth, Perkin and Stevens.

5:6-Methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic Acid (III).—5:6-Methylenedioxyhomophthalic acid (I) (1 g.) was suspended in dry xylene (100 c.c.) and the mixture heated to boiling. Selenium dioxide (0.7 g.) was added to the boiling mixture and the boiling continued for 4 hours, when the homophthalic acid gradually went into solution and a deep red solution containing a black deposit of selenium was obtained. The mixture was thoroughly extracted with dilute sodium carbonate solution and the combined extracts made just acid and evaporated to dryness. The residue was taken up in boiling water, filtered from a little insoluble matter and the filtrate treated with excess of sodium bisulphite solution and evaporated to dryness on a steam bath and then heated for half an hour at 120° in an air-oven. The residue thus obtained was twice stirred up with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid and the resulting solution evaporated to dryness on a steam bath. This residue was extracted twice with boiling benzene and benzene removed from the combined benzene extract by distillation. The residue (0.4 g.) on repeated crystallisation from water gave 5:6-methylenedioxyphthalaldehydic acid as beautiful needles, m.p. 155°. (Found: C, 55.6; H, 3.1. $C_8H_6O_4$ requires C, 55.8; H, 3.1 per cent). This acid is readily soluble in alcohol, moderately soluble in benzene and very sparingly soluble in petroleum ether.

5:6-Methylenedioxyphthalidic.—The acid (III) (0.3 g.) dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution (10 c.c. of 5%) was reduced with excess of sodium amalgam (10 g. of 4%). The aqueous solution was separated from mercury, filtered, heated to boiling and acidified. On cooling, the phthalide separated in almost theoretical yield as needles, m.p. 227°. (Found: C, 60.5; H, 3.6. $C_8H_6O_4$ requires C, 60.7; H, 3.4 per cent). The phthalide crystallised readily from water. It is readily soluble in alcohol, sparingly soluble in benzene and almost insoluble in petroleum ether.

CHEMICAL EXAMINER'S LABORATORY,
AGRA.

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